

LIPID PEROXIDATION DYNAMICS IN TOMATO VARIETIES UNDER DROUGHT STRESS AND POST-RECOVERY PERIOD

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Abstract

Drought stress is a major limiting factor for agricultural productivity, especially in water-scarce environments. In tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*), drought stress induces oxidative damage, leading to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and lipid peroxidation, which compromises membrane integrity. Malondialdehyde (MDA), a byproduct of lipid peroxidation, serves as a biomarker for assessing oxidative stress levels. This study investigates the lipid peroxidation response in the leaves of different tomato varieties under drought stress and during the post-recovery period. Nine local tomato varieties (Elim, Azerbaijan 94, Nuru, Ilyas, Yubiley 60, Mirvari, Zarrabi, Elnur, Khazar, and Shakar) were subjected to drought by withholding water for 10 days, followed by rewatering. MDA levels were measured at three stages: control, drought stress, and after 3 and 7 days of rehydration. Results show significant increases in MDA content across all varieties during drought stress, with Elnur and Zarrabi showing a 2.9- and 2-fold increase, respectively. Rehydration led to partial recovery in most varieties, with complete recovery observed in Mirvari and Azerbaijan-94 after 7 days. However, Khazar and Nuru retained higher MDA levels even after rehydration, indicating lower recovery capacity. These findings suggest that different tomato varieties exhibit distinct oxidative stress tolerance and recovery abilities, with implications for breeding drought-tolerant varieties. The study contributes to understanding drought resilience in tomatoes and provides insights for improving crop adaptation to water-limited environments.

Keywords: drought, MDA, recovery, *Solanum lycopersicum*

Introduction

Drought stress is one of the most critical environmental factors limiting agricultural productivity worldwide. As global climate change exacerbates the frequency and severity of drought events, understanding plant responses to water deficit conditions becomes increasingly urgent. Climate change further reduces water availability, efficiency, and increases drought stress in major agro-systems, especially in rain-fed ecosystems (FAO, 2020). Water scarcity impairs plant growth by disrupting various physiological and biochemical processes, including membrane integrity, pigment levels, osmotic adjustments, and water relations. It also affects secondary metabolism (Marchese et al., 2010; Chiappero et al., 2019) and stomatal closure, which in turn impairs photosynthetic activity (Ma et al., 2016; Moualeu-Ngangue et al., 2017).

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), a key vegetable crop from the Solanaceae family, is cultivated worldwide and is an essential dietary source of vitamins (A and C) and carotenoids, such as lycopene (Perveen et al., 2015). Despite large-scale cultivation, tomato production has not met demand in recent years due to abiotic stresses, including drought (Ali et al., 2021). Drought stress significantly disrupts both vegetative and reproductive processes in tomatoes, inhibiting seed development, carbon assimilation, dry matter accumulation, flowering, pollen formation, and ultimately reducing yields (Bartels et al., 2005; Nuruddin et al., 2003; Ors et al., 2016; Nephali et al., 2020; Gedeon et al., 2022).

Drought-induced oxidative stress in plant cells is caused by higher electron leakage towards O₂ during photosynthetic and respiratory processes, leading to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide anion (O₂⁻), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydroxyl radical (HO⁻), and singlet oxygen (1O₂).

This imbalance between ROS production and scavenging causes damage to cellular structures and macromolecules, including lipid peroxidation, which compromises membrane integrity (Ahmad et al., 2011; Gill and Tuteja, 2010). Lipid peroxidation is the oxidative degradation of polyunsaturated fatty acids in cell membranes, resulting in the formation of reactive aldehydes like malondialdehyde (MDA), a widely used biomarker to quantify oxidative stress. Elevated MDA levels indicate increased oxidative stress and cellular injury, making it a critical parameter for assessing drought-induced damage. In the context of crop productivity, drought stress on tomatoes is particularly detrimental. Tomatoes are highly sensitive to water scarcity, which leads to reduced photosynthesis, impaired growth, and ultimately lower yields. Given the increasing vulnerability of agriculture to climate change, breeding and selecting drought-tolerant varieties has become essential. Understanding the biochemical and physiological responses of different tomato varieties to drought stress is vital for improving drought resilience. While much research has focused on the immediate effects of drought, less attention has been given to the post-recovery phase, where plants are rewatered after drought stress. The ability to recover from drought-induced damage is a key factor in determining overall drought tolerance. Recovery involves the restoration of cellular homeostasis, repair of damaged tissues, and the reactivation of physiological processes such as photosynthesis. Monitoring lipid peroxidation during the recovery period provides insights into the plant's capacity to reverse oxidative damage and resume normal growth.

This study aims to compare the lipid peroxidation response in tomato leaves under drought stress and assess their recovery once normal watering is restored.

The results will enhance understanding of drought resilience in tomato varieties and their potential for adaptation to water-scarce environments.

Materials and Methods

Plant Growth Conditions

The study was conducted using local tomato varieties (Azerbaijan 94, Nuru, Mirvari, Zarrabi, Elnur, and Khazar) from the experimental base of the Research Institute of Vegetable-Growing under the Ministry of Agriculture of Azerbaijan. The plants were cultivated in an artificial climate chamber at $65 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, a $25^\circ\text{C}/20^\circ\text{C}$ temperature regime, and a photoperiod of 16h/8h.

Drought Stress and Recovery Treatments

Drought stress was imposed by withholding water for 10 days. After the drought period, the plants were rehydrated. Leaf samples from control, drought-exposed, and rewatered plants (after 3 and 7 days of rehydration) were ground in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until further analysis.

Determination of Malondialdehyde Content

Lipid peroxidation was determined by measuring MDA content using a spectrophotometric method based on its reaction with thiobarbituric acid at wavelengths of 523 and 600 nm (Heath and Packer, 1968). For this, 0.3 g of leaf tissue was ground with 2 ml of 0.1% trichloroacetic acid. The homogenate was centrifuged at 1000 g for 10 minutes, and 4 ml of 0.5% thiobarbituric acid solution in 20% trichloroacetic acid was added to the supernatant. The mixture was heated in a boiling water bath for 30 minutes, then rapidly cooled in ice water to stop the reaction. After centrifugation at 1000 g for 15 minutes, the optical density was measured using a Thermo Scientific Evolution 350 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (UK). MDA concentration was calculated using the formula:

$$A = (D532 - D600) / 46.5$$

Statistical analyses.

The experimental data were obtained from a study conducted with three replicates. Statistical analyses were performed using the Turkey test, with significance determined at $** p < 0.01$ and $* p < 0.05$. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

The effects of drought and rewatering on MDA content in tomato leaves are shown in Figure 1. Under drought conditions, MDA content increased significantly in all tomato varieties compared to control plants. Drought-exposed Elnur and Zarrabi varieties exhibited a 2.9- and 2-fold increase, respectively. After 3 days of rehydration, MDA levels decreased slightly in these varieties but remained significantly elevated compared to control values ($p < 0.01$). After 7 days of rehydration, MDA content in Elnur and Zarrabi leaves showed partial recovery, with reductions of 0.0012 ± 0.001 mmol/g FW and 0.0014 ± 0.002 mmol/g FW, respectively. Khazar and Nuru cultivars exhibited substantial increases in MDA levels by 2.6- and 2.1-fold under drought conditions. After 3 and 7 days of rehydration, MDA levels in Khazar leaves remained statistically significantly higher than in the control and in the leaves of Nuru cultivar, despite a decrease, the MDA content remained statistically different (0.0019 ± 0.002 mmol/g FW) from the control. In the Azerbaijan-94 variety, MDA content increased under drought stress by 0.0020 ± 0.004 mmol/g FW. After 3 days of rehydration, MDA levels decreased slightly, showing partial recovery. Complete recovery was observed after 7 days, with MDA content approaching control levels. Similarly, the Mirvari cultivar displayed a significant increase in MDA content (0.0018 ± 0.003 mmol/g FW) under drought conditions. Following 3 days of rehydration, MDA levels significantly decreased (1.29-fold) and fully recovered after 7 days (0.0013 ± 0.001 mmol/g FW).

Table 1

The level of MDA content in the leaves of tomato plants during drought and rehydration periods. Results of Turkey test: $ p < 0.01$ and $* p < 0.05$, ns-insignificant. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation.**

Varieties	Control (mmol/gr FW)	Drought (mmol/gr FW)	After 3 days of rehydration (mmol/gr FW)	After 7 days of rehydration (mmol/gr FW)
Elnur	0.0008 ± 0.001	0.0023 ± 0.002 **	0.0020 ± 0.002 **	0.0012 ± 0.001 *
Khazar	0.0010 ± 0.001	0.0026 ± 0.003 **	0.0025 ± 0.003 **	0.0021 ± 0.002 **
Nuru	0.0012 ± 0.001	0.0025 ± 0.003 **	0.0020 ± 0.002 **	0.0019 ± 0.002 **
Zarrabi	0.0009 ± 0.001	0.0018 ± 0.002 **	0.0016 ± 0.002 **	0.0014 ± 0.002 *
Azerbaija-94	0.0013 ± 0.003	0.0020 ± 0.004 **	0.0018 ± 0.002 *	0.0013 ± 0.001 ns
Mirvari	0.0013 ± 0.001	0.0018 ± 0.003 *	0.0014 ± 0.004 ns	0.0013 ± 0.001 ns

The accumulation of MDA in the leaves of tomato plants indicates cell membrane damage and lipid peroxidation to oxidative stress (Gowtham et al., 2020) Our

results demonstrate that drought stress triggered MDA accumulation in all investigated tomato varieties. On

the other hand, different tomato varieties exhibit different responses to water recovery. Elnur and Zarrabi showed partial recovery after 7 days of rehydration, while Mirvari and Azerbaijan-94 fully recovered. However, MDA levels in Nuru and Khazar varieties remained elevated even after the rehydration period.

By comparing MDA levels across varieties during drought and rewatering, this study identifies key differences in oxidative stress tolerance and recovery ability. These findings can aid in the selection of tomato varieties better adapted to drought conditions, improving crop resilience in water-limited environments. Additionally, this research provides valuable insights for breeding programs aimed at enhancing drought tolerance in tomatoes and other crops.

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